

THE ACTION OF HYDROGEN SULPHIDE ON PERMANGANATES. PART II. POTASSIUM, AMMONIUM, AND BARIUM PERMANGANATES

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The action of hydrogen sulphide on permanganates of potassium, ammonium and barium has been studied. The chief products in solution are thiosulphate, dithionate and sulphate. The precipitate contains compounds having the composition, $RO \cdot nMnO_2$.

In a previous communication (Mohammad and Ahluwalia, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 309) it was shown that compounds of varying composition, *i.e.*, $xRO, yMnO, zMnO_2, nH_2O$ were formed when hydrogen sulphide water was added to solutions of calcium and silver permanganates. It has been possible now to get some conclusive results by studying the action of hydrogen sulphide on permanganates of potassium, ammonium and barium.

Products of Reaction when Hydrogen Sulphide water is added until the purple colour of Potassium Permanganate (1%, 50 c.c.) just disappears

This stage of the reaction is called the *decolourisation* or the *neutral* stage. The solution after filtering off the dark brown precipitate, produced in the reaction, is neutral. On analysis it is found that 65% of total potassium (estimated by the cobaltinitrite method) are present in the filtrate. It is obvious that the rest of potassium is present in the precipitate in the combined state. The potassium in the filtrate is accounted for as thiosulphate, dithionate and sulphate (for methods of analysis, *cf.* Mohammad and Ahluwalia, *loc. cit.*). The formation of thiosulphate can be obviated if hydrogen sulphide water is added exactly up to the decolorisation stage. As the end-point is not sharp, the solution so obtained is found to be turbid and contains colloidal sulphur and oxides of manganese. Thiosulphate is also found to be absent if hydrogen sulphide is bubbled carefully up to the decolorisation stage. After the decolorisation stage, further addition of hydrogen sulphide makes the solution alkaline. Excess of hydrogen sulphide produces polysulphides of potassium in the solution and converts the dark brown precipitate into manganous sulphide.

Similar results are obtained when H_2S aq. is added to solutions of ammonium and barium permanganates. Sulphate is present as barium sulphate in the precipitate obtained by adding H_2S aq. to barium permanganate solution.

Analysis of the Precipitate

The precipitate obtained in the decolorisation stage is treated with strong hydrochloric acid and the chlorine evolved is absorbed in a concentrated solution of potassium iodide. This gives the available oxygen. The residual liquid is neutralised with solid sodium carbonate and aliquot portions from this are used for estimating potassium and total manganese (pyrophosphate method). The results, which are embodied in Table I (Expts. 1 & 2), show that the value for the molecular ratio of $K_2O : MnO_2$ is 1 : 2 and the value for the molecular ratio of $K_2O : MnO : MnO_2$ is 1 : 3 : 5 : 2. The analytical data obtained by using a current of hydrogen sulphide, also gives the same value of 1 : 2 for the molecular ratio of $K_2O : MnO_2$. However, the value of the molecular ratio for $K_2O : MnO : MnO_2$ becomes 1 : 4.8 : 2.1 (Table I, Expts. 3 & 4).

Morawsky and Stingle (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1878, 18, 2) obtained $K_2O \cdot 0.8MnO_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ by reducing a neutral solution of potassium permanganate by alcohol, glycerol, potassium thiocyanate or potassium oxalate. Several compounds of potassium and of many other metals of similar composition have been prepared by different methods (Mellor, "Treatise on Inorganic Chemistry", Vol XII, p. 274). These compounds are regarded as the derivatives of hydrated manganese dioxide. Gorger (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1862, iii, 66, 161) and W. Biltz (*Gott. Nachr.*, 1930, 189) regard hydrated manganese dioxide as manganous acid, H_2MnO_3 , so that manganese dioxide becomes manganous anhydride, MnO_2 , and the salts $RO, nMnO_2$, permanganites. Wright and Manke (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 53, 34) observed that the product obtained by reducing potassium permanganate with glycerol does not have the composition $K_2O \cdot 0.8MnO_2 \cdot 3H_2O$, assigned to it by Morawsky and Stingle (*loc. cit.*), for neglecting the water of crystallisation, it varied considerably in composition, e.g., $K_2O \cdot 3MnO \cdot 6MnO_2$; $2K_2O \cdot 13MnO \cdot 22MnO_2$; and $3K_2O \cdot 2MnO \cdot 18MnO_2$. It was also found by them that the product of reduction of permanganate by sulphur dioxide in the cold approximated to $K_2O \cdot 2MnO \cdot 12MnO_2$. In view of the above reports the product obtained by the action of hydrogen sulphide on potassium permanganate may have the composition $K_2O \cdot 2MnO_2 \cdot 2K_2O \cdot 7MnO \cdot 4MnO_2$ or $K_2O \cdot 5MnO \cdot 2MnO_2$ (calculated from the values given in Table I). The first composition given to the compound seems probable since in the two different sets of experiments the value of the molecular ratio of $K_2O : MnO_2$ remains constant.

TABLE I

Composition of the precipitate when the colour of $KMnO_4$ (1%, 50 c.c. containing 0.1238 g. of K) just disappears by H_2S

No.	H_2S aq.	K_2O .	MnO .	MnO_2 .	Mol. ratio, $K_2O:MnO:MnO_2$.	Mol. ratio (approx.) $K_2O:MnO_2$.
1	23 c.c.	0.0519 g.	0.1376 g.	0.1078 g.	1:3.5:2.2	1:2
2	23 c.c.	0.0518	0.1376	0.1078	1:3.5:2.2	1:2
3	Gas bubbled	0.04340	0.1554	0.0848	1:4.8:2.1	1:2
4	Gas bubbled	0.04300	0.1558	0.0843	1:4.8:2.1	1:2

TABLE II

Analysis of the precipitate obtained by adding increasing amounts of H_2S aq. to 50 c.c. of $KMnO_4$ solution (1%)

No.	H_2S aq.	$KMnO_4$ decomposed.	% Decom- position.	K_2O .	MnO .	MnO_2 .	$K_2O:MnO:MnO_2$.	$K_2O:MnO_2$ (approx.).
1	11 c.c.	0.1273 g.	25.46	0.02082 g.	0.02669 g.	0.03741 g.	1:1.7:1.94	1:2
2	16.5	0.2313	46.26	0.02554	0.06705	0.04524	1:3.48:1.92	1:2
3	22.0	0.2676	53.52	0.03024	0.07663	0.0535	1:3.3:1.9	1:2
4	27.5	0.3244	64.88	0.0407	0.08624	0.07308	1:2.8:1.94	1:2
5	33.0	0.3921	78.42	0.04565	0.09965	0.09396	1:2.9:2.2	1:2
6	38.5	0.4471	89.42	0.04563	0.1214	0.0974	1:3.4:2.26	1:2
7	44.0	0.5000	100*	0.0519	0.1376	0.1078	1:3.5:2.2	1:2
8	50.0	—	—	0.0337	0.1956	0.0348	1:7.7:1.14	—

* 100% Decomposition indicates the stage at which the purple colour of the permanganate just disappears.

In order to elucidate further the composition of the dark brown precipitate in the neutral stage, the composition of the precipitates formed in the preliminary stages of the reaction was also determined.

To solutions of potassium permanganate (50 c.c., 1%) increasing amounts of H_2S aq. were added. The precipitate obtained in each experiment was thoroughly washed and then analysed. The results of entirely separate experiments are recorded in Table II. They show:

(i) The changes in the manganese dioxide content correspond exactly with those of potassium and show a maximum at the decolorisation stage like that of potassium.

(ii) Though no constant relation is observed in the values obtained for the molecular ratios of $K_2O : MnO$, or $MnO : MnO_2$, or $K_2O : MnO : MnO_2$, yet the value of the molecular ratio of $K_2O : MnO_2$ remains constant *i.e.* 1 : 2 in all different sets of experiments. This remarkable constancy in the value for the molecular ratio of $K_2O : MnO_2$ in all the experiments and similarity in the changes of their contents in the precipitates point out the formation of the compound $K_2O \cdot 2MnO_2$. The results show that this compound is continuously formed throughout the preliminary stages of the reaction.

(iii) The amount of manganous oxide, calculated from the difference of total manganese corresponding to manganese dioxide, increases progressively with the addition of increasing amounts of hydrogen sulphide water. After the decolorisation stage, any excess of hydrogen sulphide reduces the manganese dioxide content in the precipitate though increase in the amount of manganous oxide is still noticed (Table II, Expt. 8). Considering the primary reduction of manganese dioxide (in the compound $K_2O \cdot 2MnO_2$) to be taking place according to the equation $MnO_2 = MnO + O$, if the amount of manganous oxide be calculated from the amount of manganese dioxide decomposed, it corresponds nearly with the observed amount of manganous oxide (Expts. 7 & 8, Table II. Decrease in the amount of $MnO_2 = 0.073$ g. Amount of MnO observed = 0.058 g; calculated amount of $MnO = 0.059$ g.). This shows that the reaction follows a definite course. Manganous oxide may be considered as the primary reduction product of manganese dioxide.

The concentration of the oxidising agent does not seem to have any effect on the composition of the precipitate, since 0.5% potassium permanganate solution, also yields similar results.

The above results are in agreement with those obtained by adding increasing amounts of hydrogen sulphide water to 1% solution of barium permanganate. The results are recorded in Table III. They show that the value of the molecular ratio for $BaO : MnO_2$ remains constant and is 1 : 2 as observed in the case of potassium permanganate.

TABLE III

Analysis of the precipitates when increasing amounts of H_2S aq. are added to 50 c.c. of $Ba(MnO_4)_2$ soln. (1%)

No.	H_2S aq.	$Ba(MnO_4)_2$ decomposed.	%Decomposition.	BaO. MnO. MnO_2 .			Molecular ratio $BaO : MnO : MnO_2$.	Molecular ratio (approx.) $BaO : MnO_2$.
				BaO.	MnO.	MnO_2 .		
1	11 c.c.	0.1844 g.	36.88	0.0113 g.	0.0597 g.	0.01217 g.	1 : 11.4 : 1.9	1 : 2
2	14	0.2291	45.82	0.01248	0.0760	0.01304	1 : 13.1 : 1.8	1 : 2
3	17	0.3143	62.86	0.01553	0.1011	0.01956	1 : 13.9 : 2.2	1 : 2
4	20	0.3366	67.32	0.0188	0.1105	0.0204	1 : 12.6 : 1.9	1 : 2
5	23	0.4256	85.12	0.0217	0.1437	0.02108	1 : 11.8 : 1.8	1 : 2
6	26	0.4943	98.86	0.0235	0.1700	0.02108	1 : 15.6 : 1.7	1 : 2
7	32	(i) 0.5000	100*	0.02366	0.1697	0.0239	1 : 15.5 : 1.8	
		(ii) 0.5000	100	0.02300	0.1687	0.02522	1 : 16 : 1.93	1 : 2
8	37	...	...	0.01936	0.1724	0.00478	2.3 : 44.2 : 1	
9	44	...	...	0.01574	0.1864	0.00348	4 : 105 : 1	Alkaline solution.

* 100% Decomposition represents the stage at which the permanganate colour just disappears.

In order to confirm the composition of the intermediate compounds in the neutral stage, the action of hydrogen sulphide on the compounds to which similar compositions have been assigned, was studied.

The Action of Hydrogen Sulphide on Potassium Octapermanganite ($K_2O \cdot 8MnO_2$) and Barium Dipermanganite ($BaO \cdot 2MnO_2$).

Potassium octapermanganite is prepared as a dark brown precipitate by adding 2.5 c.c. of 10% solution of glycerol to 50 c.c. of 1% potassium permanganate solution. This reaction has an induction period of about half an hour which can be shortened by adding increasing volumes of 10% glycerol. The analysis of the precipitate (Table IV) shows that the compound formed has the composition, $K_2O \cdot 8MnO_2$.

TABLE IV

Analysis of the precipitate when 2.5 c.c. of 10% glycerol are added to 50 c.c. of 1% $KMnO_4$ soln.

No.	K_2O (g.)	MnO_2 (g.)	Molecular Ratio $K_2O : MnO_2$
1	0.0369	0.2738	1 : 8.04
2	0.0370	0.2734	1 : 8.10

TABLE V

Composition of the precipitate when the colour of NH_4MnO_4 (0.5%, 100 c.c.) just disappears by H_2S .

No.	H_2S aq. (c.c.)	$(NH_4)_2O$ $= 2NH_3 + H_2O$	MnO (g.)	MnO_2 (g.)	Molecular ratio $(2NH_3 + H_2O) :$ $MnO : MnO_2$	Molecular ratio $(2NH_3 + H_2O) :$ MnO_2
1	40	0.0208 g.	0.2294	0.03652	1 : 8.37 : 1.02	1 : 1
2	40	0.0202	0.2294	0.03652	1 : 8.39 : 1.05	1 : 1
3	(1% solution)					
	80	0.0400	0.4584	0.07348	1 : 8.5 : 1.1	1 : 1
4	80	0.0412	0.4584	0.07336	1 : 8.40 : 1.1	1 : 1

The fact that the whole of the manganese is present in the precipitate and corresponds with the total available oxygen, proves the absence of any other oxide of manganese in the precipitate. These results confirm the conclusions of Morawsky and Stingle (*loc. cit.*). It appears that Wright and Manke (*loc. cit.*) must have taken an excess of glycerol which reduces further some of the manganese dioxide into manganous oxide.

Barium dipermanganite ($BaO \cdot 2MnO_2$) is prepared by adding hydrogen peroxide to 1% solution of barium permanganate until the solution became just colourless.

When aqueous H_2S is added to potassium octapermanganite or barium dipermanganite, suspended in water, each stage, *viz.*, the neutral, the alkaline and the polysulphide observed in the reaction between hydrogen sulphide and permanganates of potassium and barium, is noticed. Even the products and their relative amounts formed are comparable (Table VI, Expt. 4). It is interesting to note that though dithionate is formed in the neutral and the alkaline stages of the reaction, sulphate was found to be absent. The presence of sulphate can only be detected in the polysulphide stage. This is due to the decomposition of dithionate by hydrogen sulphide into thiosulphate, sulphate and sulphur (Dunncliff and Nijhawan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1; Mohammad and Ahluwalia, *loc. cit.*). Similar observations are made in the reactions between hydrogen sulphide and permanganates of potassium and barium. No increase in the amount of sulphate is noticeable in the alkaline stage of the reactions. Sulphate can not be detected also when H_2S aq. is mixed with precipitates obtained by the addition of H_2S into solution of potassium and barium permanganates. Since dithionate is shown to be absent in the preliminary stage of the reaction, these results point out that sulphate and dithionate are formed

by two different reactions, the dithionate being formed only by the reduction of weak oxidising agents, the permanganites, the primary products of reduction of permanganates.

The results of analysis of the precipitate obtained by adding aq. H_2S to ammonium permanganate solution (53 c.c., 0.5% and 1%) are recorded in Table V.

The results show that the value of the molecular ratio of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}$ (or better $2\text{NH}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$): MnO_2 is 1:1 instead of 1:2 which is the value for the molecular ratio of $\text{K}_2\text{O} : \text{MnO}_2$ obtained in the reduction of potassium permanganate. The composition of the compound formed may be represented as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot \text{MnO}_2$ or $\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot 2\text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{MnO}_2$. This abnormality in the high content of 'ammonium' may be due to the feebly basic nature of ammonium hydroxide. However, the results are remarkably in agreement with those obtained by Biltz (*loc. cit.*) who obtained the same compound by treating manganese dioxide with ammonia, cooled by a freezing mixture of solid carbon dioxide and pumping off ammonia. He represented hydrated manganese dioxide as permanganous acid, H_2MnO_3 and its normal salt, ammonium permanganite as $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{MnO}_3$ (*i.e.*, $\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot 2\text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{MnO}_2$).

The acidic properties of hydrated manganese dioxide are very feeble and as a result it shows a great tendency to form polymerides, polypermanganites (Cocosiuschy, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 176, 186; 1930, 293, 189). The formation of a polypermanganite may be represented thus :

In the reduction of potassium and barium permanganates, the primary reduction products are $\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot 2\text{MnO}_2$ and $\text{BaO} \cdot 2\text{MnO}_2$. These products may be regarded as the derivatives of polypermanganous acid, $\text{H}_2\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_5$, and their composition may be represented as $\text{K}_2\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_5$; BaMn_2O_5 . A similar compound is obtained from calcium permanganate.

The Alkaline Stage of the Reaction

After the neutral stage, further addition of hydrogen sulphide to a permanganate solution makes the solution alkaline. Potassium, barium or ammonium in the solution is now accounted for as $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{''}$, $\text{S}_2\text{O}_6^{''}$, $\text{SO}_4^{''}$ and OH' (titrated against a weak acid). The results are tabulated in Table VI (Expt. 1, 2 and 3).

TABLE VI

The products of the reaction in solution where H_2S is passed through solution of permanganates (1%, 50 c.c.) till the solution becomes alkaline

No.	Permanganate used.	$\%(\text{SO}_4)^{''}$.	$(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)^{''}$.	$(\text{S}_2\text{O}_6)^{''}$.	$(\text{OH})'$.	K, Ba, or NH_4 calc.	K, Ba or NH_4 obs.
1	KMnO_4	0.0905 g.	0.0160 g.	0.0024 g.	0.0123 g.	0.1092 g.	0.1093 g.
2	NH_4MnO_4	0.1040	0.0060	0.0024	0.0101	0.0524	0.0524
3	$\text{Ba}(\text{MnO}_4)_2$	0.0958	0.0044	0.0025	0.0452	0.0183	0.0183
4	KMnO_3	Nil	0.0044	0.0023	—	—	—

* * The amount of $(\text{SO}_4)^{''}$ estimated in the alkaline stage is almost the same as observed in the neutral stage of the reaction.

The alkalinity of the solution is due to the free alkali present formed by the hydrolysis of permanganites. Dunncliff and Nijhawan (*loc. cit.*) ascribe this to the adsorption of sulphate ions. The results (Table VI) obtained by us, however, do not lend support to this view.

The Polysulphide and the Final Stages

When increasing amounts of hydrogen sulphide are added, total potassium, barium and 'ammonium' comes in the filtrate and the solution assumes a yellow colour due to the formation of polysulphides. Some increase in the amount of thiosulphate and sulphate is noticeable due to the decomposition of dithionate which is found to be absent. The results are similar to those obtained in the reduction of calcium permanganate (Mohammad and Ahluwalia, *loc. cit.*). If hydrogen sulphide is passed for several hours even the polysulphides decompose, leaving behind a colourless solution. Barium in the final stage of the reaction is wholly accounted for as $(S_2O_3)^{2-}$ and $(SO_4)^{2-}$ and their values approximate to 5 molecules of barium sulphate and one molecule of barium thiosulphate. The results can be represented by the equation,

(Calculating from the experimental value $BaSO_4$, 82.3% ; BaS_2O_3 , 17.7% and the value for for the molecular ratio of $BaSO_4 : BaS_2O_3$ is 4.98 : 1).

In the case of ammonium and potassium permanganates the solution of the final stage remains alkaline. This is probably due to the following reactions :

(Desgre, *Compt. rend.*, 1926, 183, 2244, 137)

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